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Electricity demand and carbon emission in power generation under high penetration of electric vehicles. A European Union perspective

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Abstract

The European Union has set targets to reduce the greenhouse gases emissions in total energy consumption as a part of the securing the clean energy initiative and the efforts of carbon emissions reductions of 90%, compared to the 1990 ones, until 2050. The transport sector is particularly exacerbating the above problems. Focusing on their fight, European authorities have invested and continue to invest in electric propulsion. In the European Union, electric mobility has grown tremendously in the last decade. Specifically, more and more automobile industries are turning their interest in electric technology to replace conventional cars which they use internal combustion engine. This study tries to evaluate the impact of the electric vehicle penetration in the electricity demand and related emissions inside the EU, in three steps. First, the penetration of electric vehicles into the Union is evaluated through literature review, then the impact in electricity demand due to the electric vehicles penetration is estimated and finally the emission of carbon dioxide gases allocated to these changes in the electricity demand are calculated based on official data published by EuroStat. The results were calculated using the most common prognostic tools in order to identify the expected trends, and showed that the future electrification in transportation will support the efforts on reducing the carbon emissions but not that fast as it was expected as the electricity generation in EU is still based in fossil fuels at significant percentage.

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1. Introduction

The transportation means' numbers are increasing continuously through the years resulting to an increase in greenhouse gases emissions and atmospheric CO₂ in particular [1]. European Commission [2] announced that the

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Nomenclature

BEV	Battery Electric Vehicle
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
CO _{2eq}	Carbon Dioxide Equivalent
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GHG _{net}	Carbon emissions from electricity generation
Enet	Energy in network
e_{ev}	Average energy consumption by total fleet of BEVs
N_{cars}	Total number of electric cars
d_{an}	Average annual distance by car in EU
η_{ch}	Average efficiency of charging points
losses _{net}	Losses of network
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe

transportation emissions during 2014, were up to 88.912.694 Mt of CO₂ equivalents, even though according to European Environmental Agency (EEA), there was a steady reduction by almost 22 gCO₂/km (grams of CO₂ equivalent per kilometer) between the years 2010 and 2016, [3].

The effort on reducing the GHG emission was established firstly with the “Kyoto protocol” agreement of 1992, which was in force until 2015. The achievement of some targets faster than expected and the continuously increment of GHG in the atmosphere, showed the necessity for revising the targets and thus, to a new agreement. The Paris Agreement adopted on December 12, 2015, and replaced the Kyoto Protocol with a new set of targets, following this necessity. The Paris agreement, aims at mitigating the impact of climate change over the decades to come, with a mixture of measures including increment of renewables, higher energy efficiency and emissions reduction with ambitious targets. Focusing on the transportation emissions, the new target is the reduction of the GHG emission by 60% until 2050 (compared to the 1990 levels) and by 20% until 2030 (compared to the 2008 levels). Under this agreement, the Electric Vehicles (EV) emissions threshold value was set up to 95 gCO₂/km by 2021. [1,2,4,5].

However, the continuing use of internal combustion fossil fuels engine by vehicles, have made the transport sector, especially road transport, as one of the higher polluting factors in the environment. Road transport is largely responsible for greenhouse gas emissions (see Fig. 1). Although emissions began to decline in 2007, still remain high, since the reference date, of 1990. Nevertheless, a recent report of European Environmental Agency [5] showed that new passenger cars present higher average emissions by 2.8 g CO₂/km in total in years 2017 and 2018. This upward trend continued in 2019, with an additional increase of 1.6 g CO₂/km, reaching 122.4 g CO₂/km, according to provisional data from EEA [5]. This average value, even though it remains below the target of 130 g CO₂/km applied until 2019, is significantly higher than the EU target of 95 g CO₂/km by 2021, say this report [5]. According to the Eurostat [6,7], one of the main reasons for the increase in car emissions can be attributed to the growing share of the sport utility vehicle (SUV) segment. According to available data from EEA, even though the number of electric cars increased further during 2019, their market penetration is still slow [5].

According to the above, the automotive industry turned its attention to the design of electric cars due to technological conditions and environmental constrains. Electricity has been the main idea in the transport sector to reduce gas pollution and its implementation has had a positive effect on other sectors. Initially, in the energy sector, it contributes to the electrification of means of transport and the use of “pure” energy. This action can be done purely with the help of scattered production and renewable sources. Even in the environment, electric propulsion can bring significant results. The use of electric vehicles will have a positive effect on climate change with a significant reduction in harmful gases [8]. In particular, emphasis is placed on the prospect of a circular economy based on recycling. Recycling concerns the components of electric vehicles, which benefit significantly from their reuse. Finally, the most important thing is that no air pollutants are produced from their exhausts as they do not

Fig. 1. CO₂ emissions per sector of interest in the European Union, 1990–2014 (Index 1990 = 100) [1,2].

have an exhaust system, while at the same time they reduce noise levels, as they are completely silent. However, the use of electric motors will continue to contribute in part to environmental pollution, as they will continue to produce particles from brake and tire wear. Their role in public health is also important, especially for people with respiratory problems. This affects another area, that of humanity, with an emphasis on growth, prosperity and living standards. The penetration of electric cars in European countries led the scientific community to conduct research on their integration into the electricity grid. These studies use mathematical models, with assumptions, that calculate the future increase in electric cars in each country and their effect on electricity consumption and the impact of gaseous pollutants on the atmosphere.

Peter Kasten et al. [9] identified that the transition to electrification is one of the key factors in reducing air pollutants in passenger car emissions but simultaneously the increase of the electric motor is likely to cause significant problems in the management of electric network and the energy mix of each country. The above study explores two scenarios for the penetration of electric cars, 50% and 80% of the vehicle fleet in the year 2050. According to the scenario of 80% penetration, the electricity demand for BEV in relation to the total electricity demand ranges from 3%–25% in EU countries. On average, demand is defined as 9.5% by 2050 (see Fig. 2). Also, the increased penetration of electric cars has a positive impact to reduce greenhouse gases (model MOVEET).

Another important parameter arising from the penetration of electric vehicles in the distribution grid is the changing of the load curves considering the additional load demand during charging of electric vehicles. This fact has already been proven [10–13], and corresponds to increase demand for generation. As it is well known, power losses during transmission and distribution has also a significant role, increasing further this demand where the distributed energy sources are limited [10,14].

According to another study [15], electric cars in China throughout their lifetime have a greater environmental impact than conventional cars. This is a result of the energy mix, which used to generate electricity in this country and the produced energy comes from 78% of coal. Therefore, if the energy mix changes and the production of electricity from fossil fuels in the country decreases, then electric cars will be the ideal solution to reduce emissions in transport across the country. According to another study, for the same country [16], the forecast for the energy mix and greenhouse gases for the year 2030 were processed with the GREET model. The results show that coal-fired power generation will be reduced from 64% to 54%, in contrast to alternative energy sources that will increase their rates. The above difference, considering the penetration of electric cars will result to a reduction in energy density and a reduction in emissions.

This manuscript examines the role of the penetration of electric cars in European countries and the effects it may have, focusing on the gaseous pollutants on the atmosphere related to electricity generation that will feed electric cars. In this work there is an effort on combining data on greenhouse gases for the additional electricity generation demand due to integration of electric cars, considering the issues arising from the recent publications that have been discussed previously. Section 2 describes the methodology and materials used to equalize the prediction of gaseous

Fig. 2. Electricity demand from electric cars as a percentage of total electricity demand in 2050 [17].

pollutants and electricity demand scenarios. In Sections 3 and 4, the results of the research are presented and analyzed in conjunction with other researchers' work. Section 5 shows the conclusions drawn from the previous sections

2. Methods and materials

2.1. Statistical data analysis

The year 1990 was set as a milestone date for greenhouse gas emissions. Seventeen years later, emissions have fallen by 21.66% from the original level (Fig. 3). This reduction is due to the decisions and agreements signed by the EU members and resulted in the achievement of the target for the year 2020, such as limiting greenhouse gas emissions by 20% this year.

The transport sector is one of the most polluting factors in the environment. In particular, road transport accounts for 73.4% of all transport (Fig. 4). To reduce pollution in the transport sector, Europe has decided to follow a transition plan to low carbon dioxide emissions. More specifically, transport pollutants should be reduced by 60% in 2050 compared to 1990 [1,2]. In road transport, the strategy includes a gradual reduction in carbon dioxide emissions from conventional cars and their replacement by low or zero emission vehicles. In recent years, the fleet of passenger vehicles has been renewed. Electric cars have made their presence felt on the streets of Europe. The steady increase in the number of electric cars foreshadows the achievement of the goal set by the E.U. with Regulation 2019/631 [18], to reduce carbon dioxide emissions by 15% and 37.5% from 2025 and 2030 respectively from all vehicles.

Along with the increase in electric vehicles (Fig. 5), there is also an increase in the number of their charging points. For example, in the year 2019, 444, 422 more charging points were built than in the previous year. This means that in the future the electricity for charging electric vehicles will have to be increased in order to meet the needs of such cars [19].

One of the EU's goals is the complete de-carbonization of electricity generation. However, the main question is the integration of electric vehicles in the existing electricity network. In order to cover the consumed electricity, it is possible to require additional energy production. This process could lead to an increase in greenhouse gases emissions in countries that use fossil fuels to produce it and have not yet developed large units of renewable energy to cover loads.

2.2. Linear exponential model

The regression analysis is a quantitative approach model that examines the relationship between two or more variables and is useful for predicting the values of one variable relative to the values of the other. The variable x is called independent and the variable y is dependent. The mathematical model uses sampling values from statistical

Fig. 3. Greenhouse Gases, EU.-28, 1990–2017 (Index 1990=100).

Fig. 4. Share of transport energy demand by mode in 2014%, EU.-28.

Fig. 5. Total number of BEVs passenger cars in EU, 2019.

data in order to develop a straight line to predict y values for new values of x . Simple linear regression is in the form of the equation:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta x \tag{1}$$

where α is calculated, when $x = 0$ in Y . Also β is the change in the value of Y , when the value x is changed by one unit.

To the above equation must be added the term of the random error, which represents the variability in Y . This cannot be described by the independent variable x and it can be due either to other independent variables or to random variations. Therefore, the equation works under the assumption that the errors are independent and that they follow the normal distribution with mean value zero and variation for all x values. For the better understanding of the above method we could concern the following stages:

First of all, the theoretical model is presented, in order to state the set in which the independent variables that they will express the future behavior of the dependent variable, belong. One can get this result using the parallel research of different theoretical and empirical studies on this subject.

Then, the appropriate data are obtain. Here, it is very useful to show the major difficulties concerning the availability of the original data, for example to study their significant characteristics, namely accuracy and completeness, etc. Also, the review of the latest literature is of paramount importance for comparing the obtained results with those of other researches.

Next, the model used for the estimations, is developed, i.e. what is the relationship between the two variables.

The next stage concerns the statistical tests used for the reliability check of the resulted formula using the information of the theoretical model. The original model can be changed or reconstructed during the examination of the collected data, if for example, various problems concerning the assessment of the model or in the statistical examination or in both, appear. We

Finally, it must be mentioned that the obtained dependent values from this work, are based on the given values resulted from the independent variables.

It is very important to remark here the first four stages mentioned here, are based on the behavior of the phenomenon that it is examined under certain consideration, while the last of all deals with the provision of forecasts, which are very important for the future development of our system.

2.3. Exponential smoothing (Brown method)

Brown linear exponential smoothing is a method of predicting time series (for more details for time series analysis see [20–23]). The method uses all data from the past by calculating a weighted mobile medium with exponential weights for all previous data. In particular, the basic idea is to introduce a term that takes into account the possibility of a series presenting some form of trend. This tilt is updated by the same exponential smoothing tool.

1. The equation of simple exponential smoothing is given by the formula

$$A_t = \alpha Y_t + (1 - \alpha)A_{t-1} \quad (2)$$

where $0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$ is the smoothing value.

In this work, the appropriate value for the constant is related with the value of the mean square error. In fact, this value is chosen in order to minimize the above value. For this reason α is considered as equal to 0.21 for BEV. The values of t are $t = 2, 3, \dots, n$, and for the value $t = 1$, the initial condition $A_1 = Y_1$ is obtained.

2. The values of A_t (which represent the time series), can be calculated by using the simple exponential smoothing method like:

$$A'_t = \alpha A_t + (1 - \alpha)A'_{t-1} \quad (3)$$

where the values of A'_t are the normalized ones and they can be calculated using the second normalization for $t = 2, 3, \dots, n$, in time series, while for $t = 1$, the following initial condition $A'_1 = A_1$ is obtained.

3. Calculation of the difference of α_t :

$$a_t = 2A_t - A'_t. \quad (4)$$

4. Calculation of the voltage normalization for the adaptive factor b_t as:

$$b_t = \frac{\alpha}{1 - \alpha} (A_t - A'_t). \quad (5)$$

5. Calculation of future forecasts \hat{Y}_{t+h} for the future h period as:

$$\hat{Y}_{t+h} = a_t + hb_t \quad (6)$$

where the values of h , i.e. $1, 2, 3, \dots, n$ holds for projection years.

This method presented above, is rather useful to deals forecasts for future period. It is very important to note here the difference according to the simple exponential smoothing method, which provides forecasts only for the next period.

2.4. Basic forecast equation

The basic equation for predicting this study, was designed to analyze the effects of electricity generation on the penetration of purely electric cars in EU countries and consequently in increasing or decreasing carbon emissions until the year 2050.

The equation which was developed to calculate the additional demand for car's electricity is the following:

$$E_{ev} = e_{ev} \cdot N_{cars} \cdot d_{an}, \quad (7)$$

where it is considered that e_{ev} is the average typical electric power consumption of BEV in MWh/km and it remains constant, N_{cars} denotes the number of BEVs until 2050, using the above prediction methods, and d_{an} is the average standard distance traveled annually by cars in the EU in km.

The electricity demand at the BEV charging point is given from the following equation:

$$E_{ch} = \frac{E_{ev}}{n_{ch}}, \quad (8)$$

where it is calculated the average efficiency of the charging system in the EU.

The additional gross required electricity generation can be calculated from the electricity demand at the charging point and the losses of the transmission and distribution network as follows:

$$E_{net} = \frac{E_{ch}}{losses_{net}}, \quad (9)$$

where $losses_{net}$ denotes the total losses of electricity transmission and distribution per year. Thus, combining the above equations the following result for the network energy equation is estimated:

$$E_{net}(t) = \frac{e_{ev} \cdot N_{cars} \cdot d_{an}}{n_{ch} \cdot [1 - losses_{net}]}. \quad (10)$$

Finally, the carbon emissions from electricity generation arise from the equation:

$$GHG_{net}(t) = E_{net}(t) \cdot CO_2eq(t), \quad (11)$$

where $CO_2eq(t)$ the equivalent carbon dioxide emission factor (gCO₂ / MWh) per year, using the two prediction methods until 2050. It is noted that the unit of measurement for Eq. (11) is $t \cdot CO_2/year$.

Finally, it is very important to keep in mind that every mathematical model includes the probability of error. So, the models assume that the pattern of the chronological appearance of the variable's values can be observed. This kind of models can be obtained solely by giving information for the variable.

2.5. Data bases used in estimations

The updated official data for alternative vehicles according to the information of European Alternative Fuels Observatory (EAFO) for the years 2008–2018, were used for the estimations and projections of the vehicles numbers. The number of BEVs were taken also by EAFO. This European Observatory (EAFO) provides open and free information to support Member States with the implementation of EU Directive 2014/94 on the deployment of alternative fuels infrastructure. The EAFO collects national data for cars with alternative fuels from all EU Member States and European Free Trade Association (EFTA) members plus Turkey. The EAFO categorizes the vehicles based in UNECE standards [19].

EV-database website was used for the estimations of energy consumption of battery electric vehicles. It provides information only for pure electric vehicles and it contains all the range of BEVs from all manufacturers all over the world [24].

The electricity network's efficiency is a result of a division between the supplied electrical energy and the generated electrical energy. The electrical energy data were founded from International Energy Agency (IEA). The

Fig. 6. Forecasting penetration of BEVs in percentage in E.U.

IEA collects, assesses and disseminates energy statistics on supply and demand, compiled into energy balances, with high accuracy. As the data coverage has a time series stretched back to 1971, and currently covers up to 95% of global energy supply and over 150 countries, is considered as one of the highest quality data set provider. The data are collected by IEA, focusing on the quality, comparability, and alignment with internationally agreed definitions and methodologies, and close collaboration with national offices responsible for energy statistics and other relevant stakeholders [25].

The annual country data from European Environmental Agency (EEA) and its European Topic Center for Climate Change Mitigation and Energy (ETC/CME) on the average annual CO₂ emission intensity of electricity generation, was used in the calculations. The specific data set used here concerns the EEA 2017 carbon emission intensity of electricity generation. The data for CO₂ emission intensity in (gCO₂/kWh) are presented per Member State and for the EU as a whole [3].

3. Results of the research

This section presents the results of the BEV penetration into the EU, the effects it may have on the electricity grid, as well as greenhouse gas emissions from the demand for electricity by 2050. It must be also noted, that two methods used here for estimating information, first of all, for Electric Vehicles, using the latest available updated official data for alternative vehicles according to the information of EAFO. They were also used, to estimate statistics data for Electric Cars from EV-database website in order to use them for the energy consumption of battery electric vehicles. At the same time these methods were used to gain information about Electrical Energy and carbon emission intensity of electricity generation. So, it must be noted here the usefulness that the above methods present for understanding the changing in time for the electric vehicles impact on emissions.

3.1. Results of linear regression model

According to the method of linear regression, the penetration of electric cars in the countries of the European Union is presented in the following Fig. 6.

More specifically, the penetration of electric cars in all EU countries amounts to 10,593,606 in the period 2008–2030 and 42,843,085 in the period 2008–2050. Respectively, in the same periods of time, the penetration rates range from 3.95% and 15.98% in all passenger cars. The countries with the highest penetration rate of electric cars are the Netherlands, Denmark, Austria, Luxembourg, France and Sweden. These countries have turned their attention to reducing pollutants from fossil fuels and have invested in renewable energy sources and electromobility.

The relation from which the additional energy that needs to be produced for the supply of BEVs in the EU arises is shown in Fig. 7 above. It is observed that the increase in BEV will lead to an increase in the energy produced for electric propulsion. It is noteworthy that the emissions (Fig. 8) show an upward trend during the years 2020–2034, while from that point until 2050 there is a significant reduction of these emissions.

Fig. 7. Forecasting electrical production for EVs in E.U.

Fig. 8. Forecasting emissions in E.U.

3.2. Results of exponential smoothing (Brown method)

The basic equation of research (10) was also based on the method of linear exponential smoothing. This method also shows an increase in electric vehicles by 4% and 15.5% of the total fleet of conventional vehicles (Fig. 9). Similarly, electricity generated for the years 2030–2050 is maintained at high levels reaching 87,000,000 MWh (Fig. 10). In the case of carbon dioxide emissions, the curve shows a significant downward trend from 2028 onwards compared to the gradual increase from 2020 to 2027. Also, Fig. 11 shows that emissions have a negative sign in the last two years of research.

4. Discussion

This research presents both commonalities and deviations from other researchers' research on the subject of electric vehicles and the effects they have on the environment. According to research [26], BEVs save GHG in most EU countries. A smaller percentage of these countries do not reduce emissions, on the contrary, they continue to increase as their energy mix comes from fossil fuels. According to another study (Marco [27]), sales of electric vehicles in 2030 are expected to increase rapidly and reach 44 million. However, the findings of this study contradict the results of the present analysis, according to which in the year 2030 the number of BEVs will rise to about 11 million and in the year 2050 to about 42 million. In addition, [28] the impact of gaseous pollutants on the environment has been investigated, considering the life cycle of BEV in relation to conventional cars. In particular, the results of the survey concern the energy demand of BEV, which is 34% lower compared to a vehicle that consumes conventional fuels. This can lead to the transition of the conventional power grid to a different network based on the use of Renewable Energy Sources limiting the use of fossil fuels.

Fig. 9. Forecasting penetration of BEVs in percentage in E.U.

Fig. 10. Forecasting electrical production for EVs in E.U.

Fig. 11. Forecasting emissions in E.U.

The results are following the findings of others where the high penetration of electric vehicles is affecting the grid and corresponds to additional generation demand [10–14,29]. This fact makes it even clearer that in order to minimize the impact to the environment and succeed in emissions reduction offered by the electrification of the mobility (passenger cars and tracks) must be based on increasing the renewables and should be based on a smart

charging approach to avoid increment in emissions. If the goal of 100% of electricity comes from renewables then the benefit for going to 100% in electric vehicles will decrease tremendously the emissions toward the goals of EU and UN for clean energy for all and protecting the environment [3,30].

At the end, it is rather important to make some comments concerning the mathematical models used in this work. It must be mentioned that in both two methods, the prediction error has to do with the difference between the predicted and the actual value for a given period. Since the above basic equations (10) and (11) use the prediction methods, it is reasonable to consider that they contain the probability of error. Also, both models (the linear exponential model and the Brown one) are giving forecasting information and thus, they are based on values which can be taken using time series analysis. Their effort is to estimate the future values based on observations of the past and the current values for this variable. The first method, which is the most popular one, give long term results, in a good point of view. The second method, is usually used to give information for more than one future period, and allow additional conclusions and differentiated trends to be identified. Thus, their combination seems to offer a more broad view of the context, allowing better understanding on the potential perspectives [20,22].

5. Conclusions

This research has led to conclusions about the penetration of BEV and the effects that electricity demand will have on the environment with two quantitative methods. The first method, linear regression, showed that the penetration of electric cars in European Union countries would reach a significant increase of 15.98% in the year 2050. This increase will significantly affect the production of electricity approaching 90 million MWh per period. 2030–2050. However, despite this increase, gas emissions will decrease significantly from 2034 to 2050. This is logically explained as the energy mix in several European countries consists of sources with low emission rates, such as RES and nuclear power plants. Similarly, the Brown method shows similar results with very small numerical deviations. In particular, electric cars will be 15.5% in 2050, the required electricity for charging electric cars will reach about 87 million and emissions will reach negative prices in the years 2048, 2049 and 2050. Therefore, the two prediction methods converge, which enhances the validity of the results. Finally, it would be good for the construction companies and the countries themselves to promote the benefits of electric vehicles as the research concludes that the results of the BEV penetration in EU countries will have a positive impact on the goals that have been established in favor of protection of the environment in combination with the carbonation of energy production units and the increase of its alternative sources.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Emmanouil Gryparis: Data curation, Writing - original draft, Investigation, Resources, Visualization. **Perikles Papadopoulos:** Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Writing - review & editing. **Hellen C. Leligou:** Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Constantinos S. Psomopoulos:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Validation, Investigation, Writing - review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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